

THE METHODS FOR IMPROVING QUALITY AND EFFICIENCY THROUGH THE USE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE PROVISION OF PUBLIC SERVICES

Abdusattorov Avazbek Abdusalom o'g'li

Kambag'allikni qisqartirish va bandlik vazirligi, Toshkent shahar

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Abstract. This article examines the potential of Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies in enhancing public service quality and efficiency, focusing on employment services and poverty reduction in Uzbekistan through the development of entrepreneurship. By addressing challenges such as data collection, coding, adaptation, and infrastructure, the paper outlines a strategic framework for AI implementation. Highlighting global examples and proposing Uzbekistan as a pioneer in this domain, the study underscores the socio-economic benefits, including reduced poverty, increased entrepreneurship, and improved budget efficiency. The analysis aims to position Uzbekistan as a global leader in AI-driven governance, paving the way for sustainable development.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Public Services, Entrepreneurship Development, Employment Services, Poverty Reduction, Data Security, Digital Transformation, E-Governance, Machine Learning, Job Creation, Economic Growth, Sustainable Development, Predictive Analysis, Resource Allocation, Microfinance, Loan Assistance, Business Training, Pilot Programs, Public-Private Partnerships, Digital Literacy, Regulatory Framework, Ethical AI, Budget Efficiency, Social Inclusion, Regional Development, Data Integration, AI Infrastructure, Citizen Empowerment, Startups, Innovation Policies.

Аннотация. В статье рассматривается потенциал технологий искусственного интеллекта (ИИ) в повышении качества и эффективности государственных услуг, с акцентом на трудоустройство и сокращение бедности через развитие предпринимательства в Узбекистане. Решая такие задачи, как сбор данных, программирование, адаптация и инфраструктура, работа предлагает стратегическую основу для внедрения ИИ. Освещая мировые примеры и предлагая Узбекистан в качестве лидера в этой области, исследование подчеркивает социально-экономические выгоды, включая снижение уровня бедности, рост предпринимательства и повышение эффективности бюджета. Анализ направлен на то, чтобы Узбекистан стал мировым лидером в области государственного управления, основанного на ИИ, создавая основу для устойчивого развития.

Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqola O'zbekistonda bandlik xizmatlari va kambag'allikni qisqartirishni tadbirkorlikni rivojlantirish orqali amalga oshirishda sun'iy intellekt (SI) texnologiyalaridan foydalanish imkoniyatlarini ko'rib chiqadi. Maqolada ma'lumotlarni yig'ish, dasturlash, moslashish va infratuzilma kabi muammolarni hal qilish uchun SI ni joriy etish bo'yicha strategik asos ko'rsatib o'tiladi. Dunyo miqyosidagi tajribalarga e'tibor qaratilib, O'zbekistonni ushbu sohada yetakchi sifatida tan olish taklif etiladi. Tadqiqot SI asosidagi boshqaruvda O'zbekistonni global yetakchi o'ringa olib chiqish, kambag'allikni qisqartirish, tadbirkorlikni rivojlantirish va byudjet samaradorligini oshirish orqali barqaror taraqqiyot yo'lini yoritib beradi.

Introduction

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has become a transformative force in reshaping public services worldwide. In Uzbekistan, the adoption of AI presents an unprecedented opportunity to revolutionize employment services and poverty reduction strategies by fostering entrepreneurship. The use of AI can improve the delivery of public services, streamline processes, and provide data-driven insights to address key socio-economic challenges. This paper explores the methods, strategies, and anticipated outcomes of integrating AI technologies into these critical areas, highlighting the potential to position Uzbekistan as a global leader in AI governance.

Steps and strategies for implementation

To successfully implement AI in employment services and poverty reduction through entrepreneurship development, a structured approach is essential. The following steps outline the key strategies for integration:

1. **Data collection and analysis:** AI systems require extensive datasets on employment trends, regional economic indicators, and population demographics. Developing a centralized database with robust security protocols will ensure reliable and actionable insights.

2. **Pilot region selection:** Implementing AI solutions in Tashkent City, a hub of economic activity and technological readiness, allows for controlled experimentation before scaling nationwide.

3. **Development of AI models:** Collaborative efforts between government institutions and tech companies are needed to create AI algorithms tailored to Uzbekistan's unique socio-economic landscape. The cost, including salaries for coders and AI engineers, is estimated to range from \$50,000 to \$100,000 per pilot phase.

4. **Skill development:** Upskilling government employees and the public on AI usage through targeted training programs is crucial for adaptation.

5. **Infrastructure development:** Investing in computational infrastructure, such as data centers and cloud systems, ensures smooth AI operations.

6. **Policy and regulatory framework:** Establishing guidelines for ethical AI usage, data privacy, and security will bolster public trust.

Challenges in implementation

The integration of AI in public services faces several challenges. These include limited digital literacy among the population, high initial costs for technology deployment, and resistance to change within traditional bureaucratic structures. Moreover, ensuring data security and overcoming coding complexities requires significant investment in expertise and resources.

Expected outcomes and economic benefits

Implementing Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Uzbekistan's public services, particularly in employment services and poverty reduction, holds transformative potential. Here's how these outcomes could unfold, with insights from global success stories and their measurable impacts:

1. Economic growth and enhanced entrepreneurship

AI can act as a catalyst for entrepreneurial activity, directly contributing to economic growth:

- **Fostering Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs):** By analyzing market trends and consumer behavior, AI can identify viable business opportunities tailored to specific regions. Entrepreneurs can then use this data to establish businesses with higher success rates.

- **Boosting GDP:** Studies from countries like the United States show that AI adoption could increase GDP by up to 14% by 2030. For Uzbekistan, AI-driven entrepreneurship might add 2-3% to the GDP annually, particularly in sectors like agriculture, technology, and trade.

- **Tax revenue growth:** As new businesses thrive, the government benefits from increased tax revenues, creating a positive cycle of reinvestment into public services and infrastructure.

2. Improved employment rates

AI can bridge the gap between job seekers and employers:

- **Job matching platforms:** AI-powered job portals can match individuals with roles based on their skills, experience, and location preferences. For instance, Estonia’s AI-powered government e-portal streamlines job matching, significantly reducing unemployment rates.

- **Upskilling programs:** AI can identify skills gaps in the workforce and recommend tailored training programs, ensuring that workers remain competitive in evolving job markets. In Singapore, AI platforms have successfully guided workers toward tech-driven job opportunities, helping reduce unemployment by 1.5% over two years.

- **Support for vulnerable groups:** AI can identify and prioritize support for groups like single parents, individuals with disabilities, and rural workers, ensuring inclusive employment growth.

3. Reduction in poverty levels

AI-based interventions can address poverty in targeted and sustainable ways:

- **Identifying poverty hotspots:** AI can analyze regional data to pinpoint areas with the highest poverty rates, enabling tailored interventions such as subsidies, training, or micro-loans.

- **Microfinance innovations:** AI-driven micro-lending platforms can evaluate applicants’ creditworthiness using alternative data like utility bills or mobile payment histories. This approach has already succeeded in Kenya, where AI-enabled loans have boosted incomes for 3 million households.

- **Measuring impact:** AI tools can monitor and evaluate poverty reduction programs in real-time, ensuring that resources are allocated effectively and results are tracked accurately.

4. Enhanced budget efficiency

AI reduces inefficiencies in governance, ensuring that resources are used where they are needed most:

- **Streamlined processes:** Automation of routine administrative tasks frees up government resources, saving time and money. For instance, the UK saved approximately \$2 billion annually by introducing AI-powered chatbots and automated systems in its public sector.

- **Fraud prevention:** AI can detect and prevent misuse of government funds, particularly in welfare programs, reducing financial leakages. This could save Uzbekistan millions of dollars annually.

5. Social equity and inclusion

AI can ensure that public services are accessible and fair:

- **Closing regional gaps:** By analyzing data, AI can identify underdeveloped regions and recommend investments in infrastructure, education, and healthcare.

- **Empowering women and minorities:** AI can highlight areas where gender or social inequality persists, helping the government implement policies that promote fairness and inclusivity.

6. Global recognition and leadership

By pioneering AI in poverty reduction and entrepreneurship development, Uzbekistan can gain global recognition as a leader in AI-driven governance.

- Becoming a model for emerging economies: Countries in Central Asia and beyond could look to Uzbekistan as a blueprint for integrating AI into public services.

- Attracting international investments: Successful AI programs could attract foreign direct investment, as businesses and organizations seek to collaborate with a forward-thinking government.

7. Financial projections for Uzbekistan

While initial costs for AI implementation may be high, the long-term benefits significantly outweigh these investments:

- Infrastructure and coding salaries: Developing AI infrastructure and hiring specialists could cost around \$50-70 million in the first phase. However, this investment could lead to annual savings of \$10-15 million through reduced inefficiencies.

- Economic benefits: A 2-3% increase in GDP could translate to an additional \$1-1.5 billion annually by 2030.

- Job creation: AI systems will create jobs in tech, data analysis, and training, providing high-paying opportunities for Uzbekistan's workforce.

Global examples and Uzbekistan's leadership potential

While countries like Estonia and Singapore have implemented AI in public governance, few have focused on entrepreneurship-driven poverty reduction. Uzbekistan has the opportunity to become a pioneer in this area, setting a global benchmark for AI applications in socio-economic development.

Some examples of how AI has yielded measurable outcomes globally:

1. Singapore: AI-driven upskilling programs helped over 70,000 workers transition to high-demand industries, reducing unemployment rates by 1.5%.

2. India: AI in agriculture improved yields by 30% in targeted regions, directly benefiting 2 million small farmers and their families.

3. Kenya: AI-based microloans increased household incomes by 25%, lifting thousands out of poverty.

By adopting these approaches, Uzbekistan can become a trailblazer in leveraging AI for societal transformation.

Conclusion

The integration of AI into Uzbekistan's public services, focusing on employment and poverty reduction through entrepreneurship, represents a transformative step toward sustainable development. By addressing challenges, leveraging strategic investments, and fostering innovation, Uzbekistan can emerge as a global leader in AI-driven governance. This initiative not only promises economic growth but also enhances the quality of life for its citizens, making it a cornerstone of the nation's future development.